

THE FUNCTION OF SOMATISMS IN LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

Ziyadullayeva Mokhira Tagayevna

teacher of Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

Mohirazyadullayeva045@gmail.com +998976152196

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10820727>

Abstract. *In English culture, the head and body are key components. The stomach is mentioned only once in a weak way in Uzbek, while it is used frequently in English phraseological units such as "turn your stomach," "don't have the stomach for," "feel butterflies in your stomach," etc. A few traits of the emotional expressions in the two languages are similar e.g., surprise is best conveyed by the eyes, and fear is best communicated by the trunk and limbs.*

Keywords: *person, body parts, culture, somatic phraseological, feelings and emotions, skin, blue eyes, red lips.*

Describing the appearance of a person, we use the lexical means that the language provides, as well as the psychological images obtained in the language experience. Different languages give speakers not only different forms of displaying the same elements of reality, but being elements of culture, “impose” a certain idea of the world on speakers, giving a person the opportunity to describe reality in a certain way that is unique to this language. Comparative analysis of individual characteristics of vocabulary that serves to designate various realities on the material of the Uzbek and English languages has been carried out by many researchers. Body parts names are components of the so-called "basic" vocabulary, which is shared by speakers of most languages and cultures due to their physiological similarity. Nonetheless, certain body parts are assigned a more substantial role in the language than others, meaning that not all body parts are equally important. N.A. Bagdasarova [1,25] demonstrated this in particular. Her work is devoted to the study of phraseological vocabulary—the lexical expression of emotions in Uzbek and English cultures—but it also includes information about morphological vocabulary. In both languages, Bagdasarova found that the face is the most "expressive" feature of the body. However, that's where the similarities stop. She had identical results in both languages for other regions of the body. Eyes can be easily distinguished in Uzbek. The head and body are central to English culture. There is only one weak allusion to the stomach in Uzbek, but the English have a large number of phraseological units related to it turn your stomach, don't have the stomach for, feel butterflies in your stomach, etc. A few characteristics of how emotions are expressed in the two languages coincide for instance, astonishment is best shown by the eyes, and fear is best expressed by the trunk and limbs. But most of the preferences in the two languages still don't match. Particularly noteworthy is the contempt that the English express by the use of phraseological units, which include the names of limbs, while in Uzbek there is not a single word that names them at all Bagdasarova, 2004. Let us dwell on a few more studies, the purpose of which was to understand what place a certain part of the body occupies in the linguistic picture of the world of an Uzbek speaker. E. Stoyanova studied somatic phraseological units relating to such a part of the body as the eyes Stoyanova. [4,36] In the article, the researcher comes to the conclusion that, in the understanding of Uzbeks, eyes have some kind of magical power - both light (good eye, kind eye) and dark (thin, black, bad, unkind, bad, dashing, hurting eye). According to E. Stoyanova, the eye is not only the personification of the divine principle, but also acts as a symbol of the person himself, a characteristic of his physical or spiritual sides, a criterion of human abilities and skills.

Eyes reflect both spiritual qualities and skills: the eye is trained (about an experienced person); sea eye about a person experienced and vigilant in maritime affairs; envious eyes. Phraseological units associated with the eyes reflect various feelings and emotions: amazement, anger, coquetry, a strong impression of attention. D.B. Gudkov Gudkov, 2003 expresses the opinion that those parts of the human body that act as “delimiting pillars” of its borders for example: side, shoulder, chest, etc. occupy a very important place in the somatic code of culture. According to the researcher, one of the most important signs of the bodily boundary is the nose. D.B. Gudkov points out that in various phraseological units, the nose denotes a spatial boundary, the approach to which indicates the maximum approach to a person in general (for example, nose to nose, under the very nose, from under the very nose, not to see beyond one’s own nose, in phraseological units, the nose is attributed not only to the ability to smell, but also to receive information in general (keep your nose in the wind, poke your nose). The nose, as the most visible part of the face, can metonymically replace the person as a whole (from nose to nose). As the researcher notes, the shape and size of the nose are one of the most characteristic features of appearance, the nose is unheroic and non-lyrical. [3,50-61] G.E. Kreidlin have conducted a number of studies on the semiotic conceptualization of individual somatic objects Kreidlin, Pereverzeva. Researchers note that the head has a special function that is not characteristic of other parts of the body - mental. This is reflected in such language units as come to the head, headless, think with the head, big-headed. Researchers distinguish three functions of the shoulders. Carrying weights: put on the shoulders; ligament of the head and neck with the body: the head from the shoulders; the role of the border between the past and the future of man: twenty years of work behind him. It is noted that when describing a person's appearance, special attention is paid to the face and its parts, that the face reflects the feelings and experiences of a person, as well as the attitude towards another: to change in the face, the face is stretched out, to read something in the face; a person can also identify a person as a whole, as a social unit.[2,235-240] The nose and nostrils have common functions associated with breathing, smelling and the penetration of objects from the outside world into the human body: he sighed through his nostrils, the nose began to smell. When describing the neck, special shapes and sizes are distinguished: swan neck, long / short neck, as well as flexibility and beauty. The neck is involved in many behavioral acts and actions of a person: hanging on the neck, twisting the neck, bending the neck. The authors further note that there are several meanings for the word chest in Uzbek. If we are talking about the upper part of the front side of the body, then this is the receptacle of vital organs, which is responsible for the ability to breathe: breathe deeply, the chest heaves, sways, worries, in addition, it is also a protective or attacking means in difficult situations: stand up with your chest to protect, expose your chest. Like the container of the heart, the chest also contains emotions: fear has settled in the chest. From an aesthetic point of view, when describing the female breast, size and shape are emphasized. Aesthetically attractive in Uzbek culture is considered a large, lush, high, strong chest, and small breasts are considered unfeminine. Negatively evaluated sunken / skinny / drooping / flabby breasts, as well as old.

From our point of view, such an assessment is natural, since such characteristics as strong, elastic, high describe a healthy breast that can feed children. Researchers also note that in Uzbek many expressions are associated with this function of the female breast: to apply to the breast, to breastfeed. The same is true for a man: aesthetically attractive is the wide, strong chest characteristic of a healthy man this is probably the reason for the function of the chest as a protective barrier.

The second part of the study is devoted to highlighting the signs of somatic objects and their meanings. There are 1) structural features; 2) physical signs; 3) the main functional features of somatic objects. Structural features include surface properties: corns on the finger, wrinkles on the forehead and the presence of voids (ear hole, flew into one ear - flew out into the other). Physical signs include shape, size, color, temperature, sound, dryness, etc. Color is not significant for all parts of the body: usually eyes, face, hair, skin. The color of a somatic object may indicate that a person belongs to a certain ethnic, social, and even age group (pink heels, a yellowed face). Stereotypically beautiful in Uzbek culture are white skin, blue eyes, red lips. A change in color can mean a change in the physical state (turned green, blushed) or the emotional state of a person (turned pale with anger, blushed with anger, as well as a change in external conditions: sunburn). The researchers note that in the Uzbek language the shape and size are widely represented, and to a lesser extent - signs associated with the functioning and movement of body parts. The temperature is associated not only with the physical, but also with the emotional states of a person. The functions of somatic objects are determined, on the one hand, by the anatomical structure of the human body, and, on the other hand, by the physiological and social tasks of a person. Dysfunctions often testify to physiological functions: the tongue becomes numb, the legs become stiff. The authors refer to non-physiological functions, for example, cultural and social: shake hands, make eyes, as well as communicative and aesthetic, which is manifested in gestures. As noted by G.E. Kreidlin and A.B. Volatile Kreidlin, Volatile, an important feature for many parts of the body is size. Physiological size plays a big role in the overall aesthetic assessment of the body: for example, large eyes, but short arms. In addition, such characteristics can reflect the essence of a person: long tongue, emotions make big eyes. The internal structure of a body part: bony shoulders is highlighted. Separately for the shoulders, the category of openness / closeness is considered which may be significant for other parts of the body: different degrees of openness of the shoulders receive different aesthetic assessments in different cultures.

Thus, somatisms are an important part of the lexical composition of the language and carry information not only about the physical condition of a person, but also about the perception of the body by native speakers of the language and culture, the aesthetic norms adopted in this cultural community. This explains the steady interest in the study of this area of reality.

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